

Nonlocality of Particle Properties and Quantum Mechanics

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Classical mechanics and even classical statistical mechanics depend on properties of a particle being defined at each point (x,t) . We argue that quantum mechanics does not impose this locality, even for a free particle. In a previous note (1), we argued that $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ ((1a)) and $d/dt \text{ Action} = -E$ ((1b)) for the case of $v=x/t$ with x and t being varied separately. V (velocity), however, is really a constant and so one should not vary x and t separately without a constraint. In (1), we suggested x and t fluctuations to be linked to d/dx and d/dt , but in this note, we consider the idea that a property of a quantum particle may not be defined at a particular point in space and yet may be very real, such as momentum. Experimentally, momentum may be measured, but even classically it is measured at (x,t) only as an approximation because an interaction must occur.

If quantum properties are not measured locally, one must still be able to distinguish between say p_1 and p_2 (momenta), otherwise one should not use the concept of momentum. If one does not distinguish locally, then one should distinguish globally. How can this be done? It seems one has to shift to the idea of probability functions and argue that distinguishable momentum probability functions $P(p/x)$ are orthogonal over space, but not fully distinguishable at any specific point x . In other words, $P(p/x)$ may not be a real probability as in classical statistical mechanics.

In order to find the probability $P(p/x)$, we suggest that one may convert ((1a)) and ((1b)) into eigenfunction equations.

Classical Mechanics

A main idea of classical mechanics seems to be that one knows properties of a particle at each (x,t) value. In fact, this is an approximation because an accelerating particle is changing its velocity at (x,t) and velocity is not strictly known at x or even in dx . Nevertheless, the idea of knowledge of particle properties at x and t seems to be key and this is extended to classical statistical mechanics.

Classical trajectories may be computed by minimizing the action = Integral $L dt$, where L is the Lagrangian. This leads to Lagrange's differential equation. We argued in (1), that one may consider a constant v (velocity) Lagrangian and set $v=x/t$. By varying x and t separately, one obtains ((1a)) and ((1b)) i.e.

$$d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d\text{Action}/dt = -E \quad ((1b))$$

For example, for a relativistic free particle $\text{Action} = t(-m_0) \sqrt{1-vv}$ where $v=x/t$.

In ((1)), we argued that this was due to fluctuations because technically x and t should not be varied separately. In this note, we argue that varying x and t should perhaps be interpreted as

considering particle properties to be nonlocal. In other words, there is a p (momentum), but one does not consider it a specific (x,t) . It may be noted that dx classically is a large distance in the quantum mechanical realm. Thus, dx being small classical (as in the derivative limit) does not mean a tiny distance quantum mechanically. If this is the case, one may ask: How may one then distinguish between different p values at x ? We argue that distinguishability occurs globally over a large range of x . This implies that there should be a function $F(p,x)$ which is responsible for this distinguishability i.e. orthogonality:

$$\int dx F(p_1,x) F(p_2,x) = \text{kronecker delta}(p_1,p_2) \quad ((2))$$

How may one interpret such a function $F(p,x)$? We argue that it seems one must consider it to be some kind of probability. Furthermore, one expects it to display invariance in space because ((1a)) does not depend on the x point at which the derivative d/dx is performed.

One may note that ((1a)) and ((1b)) may be converted into eigenvalue equations. The point of this is that certain eigenvalue equations automatically yield real eigenvalues and orthonormal eigenfunctions. The real eigenvalues map to particle properties and the eigenfunctions are distinguishable over space i.e. their inner product is zero if they represent different values of a property.

Before considering an eigenfunction for momentum p , one may ask why momentum is used as a property instead of velocity. For example, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2=m_3v_3$ etc implies that a given p maps into many different mass, v (velocity) pairs. It may be noted that both p and v are physical quantities, so why should one be used and not the other? We argue that it is p which is important in impulse hits while v is important in an acceleration picture. Thus, by choosing p over v , one chooses impulses as the physical driving force in quantum problems with a potential and not acceleration. Acceleration only appears through changes in a average kinetic energy calculation. By choosing p as the important variable, one sees that the physical position of the particle is not linked clearly to the property i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ means that at a given t , the v_1 particle will be at one x point and the v_2 at another. By ignoring locality, the actual position of the particle with momentum p is not the key idea.

An eigenvalue equation may be readily created from ((1a)) i.e.

$$i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i x \frac{dAction}{dx}) = p \exp(i x \frac{dAction}{dx}) \quad ((3))$$

This is also equivalent to $\exp(ipx)$ which is invariant throughout space. Thus, one could establish the eigenvalue simply using invariance without resort to ((1a)) i.e. the classical action, but using the classical action shows how quantum mechanics differs from classical mechanics.

The consequences of ((3)) or $\exp(ipx)$ are interesting as a wavelength is established in space of the order $1/p$ where p is momentum. Given that we argued against locality, the wavelength establishes a quantitative nonlocality for each p . This is interesting because in classical mechanics, v is associated with x and t and not p . $\exp(ipx)$ also has the form of a wave, a probability wave. It is complex suggesting that $\exp(ipx)$ is an unusual type of probability, but we argue that this is fine as $P(p/x)$ is not clearly defined i.e the particle property is not clearly

defined at a point x , so it may be complex. Furthermore, $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ are orthogonal.

Acceleration Picture

Classical mechanics is based on an acceleration picture which is automatically local. We have argued that quantum mechanics is not local and have used p (momentum) as the main variable which is not fixed to a specific velocity i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. How can one reconcile the two? If one considers a bound quantum system, $\exp(ipx)$ may be replaced with a statistical ensemble $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. This suggests that the unusual complex probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ interfere (add/subtract) unlike classical probabilities which are positive and just add. Nevertheless, the ensemble is still based on momentum p and not v . Each p represents a wavelength $1/p$ i.e. is nonlocal. To create a local object, one may calculate the average $\langle p \rangle$ and then divide by $1/2m$.

$$KE(x) = \left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] / \left[\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] \quad ((4))$$

$KE(x)$ changes with x and so an acceleration is present in the “average” system.

Case of Gravity

Gravity is strongly based on the idea of acceleration i.e. particles with m_1 and m_2 have the same gravitational acceleration. Alternatively, one has curved space in General Relativity. By arguing that quantum properties of a particle (e.g. p) may be nonlocal, it seems that one argues that identical acceleration and curved space are average ideas when applied to $\exp(ipx)$ which is linked to a wavelength (of the order $1/p$) and does not track instantaneous changes from x to $x+dx$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we reinterpret the notion of changing x and t independently in $v=x/t$ used in a constant velocity classical action $\int dt L$. Independent changes in x and t do not necessarily represent fluctuations, but represent nonlocality. That is: $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ means that momentum p a property of a particle, is nonlocal.

In classical mechanics there is locality, but in quantum mechanics, properties such as momentum are not seen as holding at each (x,t) . In such a case, one must distinguish between different p values over space which suggests orthonormal probability functions $F(p_1,x)$ and $F(p_2,x)$. It is known from linear algebra that certain eigenvalue equations yield real eigenvalues (representing physical properties) and orthonormal eigenfunctions. The eigenfunctions need not be real as one does not really know the property of a particle at each (x,t) .

To find momentum eigenfunctions, one may use $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ and create $\exp(i d\text{Action}/dx x)$ which is equivalent to $\exp(ipx)$. This yields a real p and orthogonal eigenfunctions and also includes invariance in space which is necessary because $d\text{Action}/dx=p$ holds at any x point.

$\exp(ipx)$ (related to $\exp(i\text{Action})$) is of the form of wave with a wavelength proportional to $1/p$, so physical consequences are large. Because probabilities may add, one may form combinations of $\exp(ipx)$ which will also have crests and troughs which are observable physically (e.g. two slit experiment, bound states).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)